

Experimental Design and Results for Evaluating MDDPlatform

Adel Vahdati, Raman Ramsin

Department of Computer Engineering, Sharif University of Technology Azadi Avenue, Tehran, Iran
adel.vahdati97@sharif.edu , ramsin@sharif.edu

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This document provides supplementary materials for the paper “Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model transformation as a service”. It includes a detailed description of the experimental design, covering setup, execution steps, and evaluation methods for assessing scalability, reusability, and collaboration in model-driven development. It also presents the results of the experiment, including participant feedback, evaluation questionnaires, and outcome analysis. Together, these materials offer comprehensive insights into both the experimental procedure and its findings.

1. Experiment Design

The goal of this experiment is to investigate to what extent the proposed approach has been able to improve scalability, reusability, and collaboration in creating software modeling.

1.1. Experiment Description

To conduct the experiment, we intend to implement a part of an online product ordering system using the proposed approach. Since this experiment will be carried out by different individuals, an initial analysis of this system has been presented so that all participants have a similar view of the problem. For this purpose, we assumed that this system was examined during the Event Storming event with stakeholders, and the output of these sessions was modeled in the form of the proposed CRAC metamodel. The output of this analysis is provided to each participant in the form of graphical diagrams along with textual explanations.

1.2. Experiment stages

The proposed approach (MDDPlatform) is deployable in the cloud and can be accessed remotely via the internet. However, for this experiment, we will run it locally and proceed with the experiment based on the steps that will be described. For ease of use, a tutorial video of each step is recorded as a separate file and uploaded on the internet that is accessible to each participant. This experiment is conducted in several stages, which are as follows:

1. Platform Preparation
2. Loading pre-defined & proposed packages
3. Defining the problem domain and creating domain models
4. Defining the model-driven development (MDD) process and running it
5. Code generation

Each stage consists of a set of steps that will be explained in the following sections.

1.3. Platform Preparation

To launch the local version of MDDPlatform, you need to install Docker Desktop. MDDPlatform is provided in the several Docker images. The MDDPlatform platform uses RabbitMQ for sending and receiving messages, and its database is based on MongoDB. To prepare and launch the platform, you can follow the necessary steps according to the guidance document and tutorial video provided.

1.4. Loading pre-defined & proposed packages

MDDPlatform provides the ability to define domain-specific languages, create instances of model transformation patterns, and define MDD processes. To speed up the operationalization of MDDPlatform, a set of domain-specific languages, transformation patterns, pattern instance templates, and two MDD processes have been defined that are reusable within the MDDPlatform environment. To use them, you only need to add these packages to your local version once after preparing and launching the platform. To do this, you can reuse the concepts, domain-specific languages, transformation patterns, and pre-defined MDD processes according to the guidance document and tutorial video provided.

1.5. Defining the problem domain and creating domain models

MDDPlatform provides the ability to systematically manage the problem domain and domain models at different abstraction levels. To start creating an online ordering system, you first need to define the problem domain and domain models at different abstraction levels. This is done in the following steps. How to define the problem domain, break it down into subdomains, and define domain models at different abstraction levels are explained in the tutorial video. In this stage, you define the problem domain, subdomains, and domain models according to the guide file and tutorial video.

1.6. Defining, configuring, and executing the MDD processes

To further guide and automate the model-driven development process, MDDPlatform provides the ability to define, configure, and execute the process. A high-level process consists of phases, activities in each phase, and tasks in each activity. These tasks are either automatically executed or require human intervention to perform a task. Automatic tasks are of the type of model transformations. Manual tasks are of the type of adding analysis and design information to refine the model. To perform this step of the experiment, the following steps need to be taken:

1. Defining the MDD process
2. Configuring the process
3. Executing the process

In stage 2, an examples of the MDD process has been added to the local version of MDDPlatform, and participants use this processes for this experiment, so there is no need to define a new process. However, the tutorial video explains how to define a MDD process. Now we need to configure the existing process. Configuration means specifying the input and output models of these tasks. The process configuration is explained in the guidance document and tutorial video.

After configuring the process, an executable process is automatically created that the user can run it. During the process execution, model transformations are automatically executed. The process execution proceeds automatically through a chain of tasks. If we encounter a task during the process execution that requires human intervention, the process execution will be paused until the user completes the information or task, and then the process execution will resume. Finally, with the execution of the last task of the process, the process execution is completed. The tutorial video shows details on creating an executable process and running it.

1.7. Code generation

After successfully running the MDD process, the final solution models need to be converted into code. For this purpose, we need a process to convert the model into text. In stage 2, an example of a process for converting the model into C# code has been added to the local version of MDDPlatform. Therefore, by configuring and executing this process, we can convert the output models into C# code. How to do this is explained in the guidance document and tutorial video. Finally, the generated code can be downloaded in a Zip file.

1.8. Experiment Questionnaires

After completing the experiment, each participant will answer two online questionnaires and express their opinion about each of the statements presented by choosing one of the following options: ‘completely agree’, ‘agree’, ‘not sure’, ‘disagree’, or ‘strongly disagree’. In addition, participants can provide additional explanations about these statements. The first questionnaire aims to determine whether the proposed approach and MDDPlatform have been able to:

1. Help manage complexity.
2. Improve the reusability of the artifacts.
3. Enhance scalability.
4. Facilitate collaboration.

Table 1: The first questionnaire: evaluation from the perspective of scalability, reusability and collaboration

No.	Statement
1	Deploying MDDPlatform on the internet, without the need for installation on a local machine, facilitates remote data access and collaboration among distributed team members.
2	The ability to load specific domain languages, predefined transformation patterns, and processes in MDDPlatform facilitates reuse of previous artifacts and reduces the initial cost of adopting a model-driven approach.
3	The ability to search for specific domain languages and models based on them in MDDPlatform improves finding and reusing previous artifacts.
4	Breaking down the problem domain into subdomains and creating models at different abstraction levels helps manage complexity in MDDPlatform.
5	Breaking down the problem domain into subdomains and creating models at different abstraction levels enables systematic description of the problem domain in MDDPlatform.
6	Decomposing the problem domain into subdomains and assigning each subdomain to a group of modelers can serve as a basis for design and modeling task assignments and improve teamwork and collaboration in MDDPlatform.
7	In MDDPlatform, the ability to create multiple granular models at a specific abstraction level that describe the problem from different perspectives helps manage complexity both at the metamodel definition level and at the model creation and description level.
8	Providing model transformations in the form of parametric patterns with the ability to instantiate and configure them in MDDPlatform improves reuse of transformations.
9	The ability to define a model-driven process and its automatic and semi-automatic execution in MDDPlatform helps manage complexity and guide the execution of model transformations at different levels compared to the ad hoc approach.
10	The ability to define and configure a model-driven process in MDDPlatform facilitates reuse of design and architecture patterns for other projects.
11	The ability to define a chain of transformations in the form of a pipeline or high-level process in MDDPlatform provides the possibility of applying transformations incrementally.
12	In MDDPlatform, the ability to define manual tasks during the MDD process or model transformation pipeline facilitates interrupting the transformation process and reviewing and revising the transformation results up to that point.
13	In MDDPlatform, it is possible to define multiple configurations for a MDD process. By defining a configuration for each subdomain of the problem, it is possible to collaborate among different teams and run the MDD processes concurrently for different subdomains.

No.	Statement
14	Providing model specification in a hierarchical structure (model concepts, instances of each concept, property values of each instance, and the relations among them) enables lazy loading of information and improves scalability regarding large models in MDDPlatform.
15	When describing a model in MDDPlatform, if a member of the modeling team changes the model, these changes are simultaneously propagated to other members working on that model. This improves collaboration capabilities.
16	In MDDPlatform, the ability to automatically merge information from one model into another model with the same or different metamodel provides the possibility of reusing all or part of existing model data.

To assess the usefulness and ease of use of MDDPlatform, participants are asked to express their opinion regarding each of the statements in the second questionnaire.

Table 2: The second questionnaire: evaluating the usefulness and ease of use of the MDDPlatform tool

No.	Statements
1	Using MDDPlatform accelerates modeling, model transformation, and code generation tasks.
2	Productivity increases with the help of MDDPlatform.
3	The proposed approach in MDDPlatform is an effective method for model-driven development
4	The MDD process is facilitated using MDDPlatform.
5	MDDPlatform is a useful and practical tool for model-driven development.
6	It is easy to learn MDDPlatform.
7	The way to use MDDPlatform is understandable and transparent.
8	MDDPlatform is flexible.
9	The MDDPlatform tool can be controlled by the user.
10	MDDPlatform is easy to use.
11	It is easy to gain skills and experience in MDDPlatform.

2. Experiment Result

After gathering the information of questionnaires, we have used Likert scales to assign weights to the five alternative options that convey the opinion of participants about the statements of questionnaires: Strongly agree=5, Agree = 4, Not sure = 3, Disagree = 2, and Strongly Disagree = 1. The demographic information of the experiment's participants is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Demographic information of participants

Participant No.	Academic Degree	Industry Experience (Years)	Current Status	Number of Projects Participated In	Level of Familiarity and Experience					
					Modeling & Modeling Language	MDE & MDD	Model Transformations Languages	Modeling Tools	Software Development Methodologies	Design Patterns & Architecture
1	MSc	15	Professional	5-7	4	2	2	2	4	4
2	MSc	5	Academic	5-7	5	5	5	5	4	4
3	MSc	6	Professional	3-4	3	1	1	3	4	4
4	PhD	2	Professional	8-10	4	3	3	2	5	3
5	PhD	3	Academic	3-4	5	4	4	4	5	4
6	BSc	5.5	Both	8-10	2	2	1	2	3	5
7	PhD	0.6	Professional	1-2	5	5	5	5	4	3
8	PhD	12	Professional	10+	5	5	4	4	4	4
9	BSc	1	Academic	1-2	3	3	3	2	3	2
10	PhD	4.5	Professional	5-7	3	4	2	2	5	3
11	MSc	10	Academic	3-4	3	4	3	3	4	4
12	PhD	15	Professional	10+	5	4	3	4	5	5
13	PhD	10	Academic	5-7	4	3	2	3	3	3
14	MSc	8	Academic	10+	4	4	4	4	4	4

Level of Familiarity : too much = 5; a lot = 4; intermediate = 3; little = 2; very little = 1;

2.1. Questionnaire 1

In the first questionnaire, we seek to evaluate the impact of MDDPlatform on the salacity, reusability, and collaboration from the MDD perspective. The answers of the participants in the experiment to the first questionnaire are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: The answers to the first questionnaire

No.	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13	Q14	Q15	Q16
1	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4
2	5	4	4	5	2	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	3	5	3
3	5	5	5	4	4	4	3	4	5	3	5	5	5	4	4	5
4	5	4	3	5	4	3	5	4	4	4	3	5	4	4	3	3
5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
6	4	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5
7	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	4	5
8	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	3
9	5	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	2	3
10	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	4	3	5	5	5
11	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
12	5	5	5	4	5	3	4	5	4	4	3	4	4	5	3	4
13	4	5	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	3	5	4	5	3	5	5
14	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Average	4.71	4.57	4.43	4.5	4.29	4.36	4.43	4.43	4.5	4.36	4.36	4.5	4.29	4.14	4.07	4.21
Min	4	3	3	3	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	4	3	3	2	3
Max	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
SD ¹	0.47	0.65	0.76	0.65	0.83	0.84	0.76	0.51	0.65	0.74	0.84	0.52	0.73	0.86	0.92	0.89

Figure 1: Statistical information of questionnaire 1

Figure 2: Aggregation of responses in the first questionnaire

¹ Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 5: The percentage of responses to the first questionnaire

We categorize the statements of this questionnaire into three groups: The statements that evaluate the impact of MDDPlatform on the scalability (Q4, Q5, Q7, Q9, Q11, Q14), the statement that evaluate the impact of MDDPlatform on the reusability (Q2, Q3, Q8, Q10, Q16), and the statement that evaluate the impact of MDDPlatform on the collaboration (Q1, Q6, Q12, Q13, Q15). We define three statistics based on these categories including scalability average score, reusability

average score, and collaboration average score. For each participant, these statistics are calculated according to these formulas:

$$\text{Scalability. average. score}_i = \frac{Q_{i,4} + Q_{i,5} + Q_{i,7} + Q_{i,9} + Q_{i,11} + Q_{i,14}}{6}$$

$$\text{Reusability. average. score}_i = \frac{Q_{i,2} + Q_{i,3} + Q_{i,8} + Q_{i,10} + Q_{i,16}}{5}$$

$$\text{Collaboration. average. score}_i = \frac{Q_{i,1} + Q_{i,6} + Q_{i,12} + Q_{i,13} + Q_{i,15}}{5}$$

$Q_{i,j}$ = The response of participant i to the Statement j (Q_j)

Figure 3: Scalability average score

Figure 4: Reusability average score

Figure 5: Collaboration average score

2.2. Questionnaire 2

In the second questionnaire, we evaluate the MDDPlatform usability and ease of use perspective. The answers of the participants in the experiment to the second questionnaire are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The answers to the second questionnaire

No.	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4
2	3	3	5	5	5	2	4	4	4	3	2
3	3	3	4	5	5	3	3	4	5	5	5
4	3	3	5	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	4
5	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	4
6	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	3	5	5
7	5	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	4
8	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4
9	4	4	4	4	3	2	2	3	3	3	4
10	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	5	5	4
11	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	5	4	4
12	5	4	3	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	3
13	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	3	4	4	4
14	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Average	4.14	3.86	4.36	4.57	4.36	3.57	3.93	3.79	4.14	3.93	4
Min	3	3	3	4	3	2	2	3	3	3	2
Max	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
SD	0.86	0.66	0.63	0.51	0.63	0.94	0.83	0.7	0.66	0.83	0.78

Figure 6: Statistical information of questionnaire 2

Questionnaire 2

Figure 7: Aggregation of responses in the second questionnaire

Table 7: The percentage of responses to the second questionnaire

The statements of this questionnaire are divided into two category: The statements that examine the usability of MDDPlatform (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6), and the statements that examine the MDDPlatform ease of use (Q7, Q8, Q9, Q10, Q11). We define two statistics based on these categories including usability average score, and ease of use average score.

For each participant, these statistics are calculated according these formulas:

$$Usability.average.score_i = \frac{Q_{i,1} + Q_{i,2} + Q_{i,3} + Q_{i,4} + Q_{i,5} + Q_{i,6}}{6}$$

$$EaseOfUse.average.score_i = \frac{Q_{i,7} + Q_{i,8} + Q_{i,9} + Q_{i,10} + Q_{i,11}}{5}$$

Figure 8: Usability average score

Figure 9: Ease of use average score